

Implicit Learning of Socio-Emotional Contents in Autism

Andrei Costea^{1,2*}, Răzvan Jurchiș¹, Andrei Preda¹, Adrian Opre¹

1 – Cognitive Psychology Laboratory, Department of Psychology, Babeș-Bolyai University,
Romania

2 – Department of Socio-Human Research, Romanian Academy, Cluj-Napoca Branch, Cluj-
Napoca, Romania

*Correspondence should be addressed to Andrei Costea at andrei.costea@ubbcluj.ro

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4 **ABSTRACT**
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7 To date, the cognitive mechanisms generating social deficits in autism spectrum disorders
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9 (ASDs) remain insufficiently understood. This study aims to investigate implicit learning (IL) in
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11 individuals with ASD by using socio-emotional stimuli. The current literature on IL in ASD
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13 presents mixed evidence, with some studies suggesting deficits and others indicating intact or
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15 even superior functioning. We hypothesize that socio-emotional stimuli, as opposed to simple or
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17 artificial stimuli, may reveal IL deficits in individuals with ASD due to their atypical processing
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19 of social cues. Participants will include individuals with a confirmed ASD diagnosis and
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21 typically developing (TD) individuals. Sample size will be determined by a Bayesian stopping
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23 rule Using a socio-emotional artificial grammar learning task, participants will be instructed to
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25 memorize sequences of emotional facial expressions without explicit awareness of the presence
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27 of underlying grammatical rules. Following the acquisition phase, we will assess participants'
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29 classification accuracy of novel sequences and their awareness of the acquired knowledge. Our
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31 primary objectives are to evaluate overall acquisition, explicit learning, and IL differences
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33 between ASD and TD groups, as well as to investigate potential compensatory processing. Our
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35 primary hypotheses suggest that individuals with ASD will exhibit lower a global test accuracy,
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37 a greater explicit learning effect, and a lower IL effect, and a higher reliance on explicit
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39 structural knowledge compared to TD participants. If our primary hypotheses are confirmed,
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41 these findings could be incorporated into an extended cognitive model of social deficits in –
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43 some forms of – ASD.
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53 *Keywords:* Implicit learning, socio-emotional structures, autism spectrum disorders, subjective
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55 measures of awareness, compensatory processing.
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4 1 INTRODUCTION

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7 Imagine someone is learning to ride a bicycle. Initially, every wobble and tumble teaches them
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9 something about balance, but they might not consciously grasp the mechanics behind it. Over
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11 time, they become proficient, effortlessly gliding through the streets without a second thought to
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13 the intricate coordination of muscles and balance. For decades, cognitive scientists have sought
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15 to understand how the human mind can perform such complex tasks. Building upon Reber's
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17 (1967) seminal paper, numerous scientists now support the idea that the human cognitive system
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19 can unintentionally acquire information from the environment without conscious awareness. This
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21 phenomenon is known as implicit learning (IL). In essence, unlike explicit learning, IL occurs
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23 when individuals absorb information from their surroundings without intending to do so. They
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25 may not be subjectively aware of the knowledge they have acquired – meaning they cannot
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27 accurately verbalize the cognitive structures that they have learned – yet this knowledge
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29 nevertheless enhances their behavioral performance.

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36 Far from being a purely theoretical concept confined to laboratory settings, IL is frequently
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38 posited as the cognitive substrate for the development of social cognition and intuition
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40 (Lieberman, 2000; Norman & Price, 2012). Anecdotally, consider individuals' almost
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42 instantaneous ability to discern the emotional state of a loved one based on a rapid perception of
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44 only subtle cues, such as a slight modulation in tone indicating – for instance - sadness,
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46 imperceptible to conscious awareness. This intuitive understanding may occur without direct
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48 access to the underlying information, reflecting a learned pattern of behavior informed by IL that
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50 helps us navigate complex social environments.

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56 Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASDs) are characterized by social intuition deficits (e.g., Brosnan
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58 et al., 2016). Given that IL is described as one of the cognitive processes that enables the

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4 formation of social intuitions, researchers have investigated if individuals with ASD have an
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6 overall IL deficit. The literature presents mixed evidence, with some studies finding IL
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8 impairments in ASD (e.g., Gidley Larson & Mostofsky, 2008; Mostofsky et al., 2000) while
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10 others failed to find such evidence (e.g., Barnes et al., 2008; Mayo & Eigsti, 2012) or, even
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12 found superior IL functioning in ASD (e.g., Virág et al., 2017). Importantly, Foti et al. (2015)
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14 conducted a meta-analysis that included the majority of the studies investigating this hypothesis
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16 and concluded that the extant evidence does not support the IL deficit in ASD hypothesis.
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18 Despite the conclusion, this research topic continues to spark significant interest in the scientific
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20 community. For instance, in a recent study, Treves et al. (2023) conducted a comparison between
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22 individuals with a reported diagnosis of ASD and individuals with typical development (TD) by
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24 using a visuo-motor learning task. In it, participants responded to the changing location of a
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26 target stimulus. Unbeknownst to them, the location was determined by a complex rule. Learning
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28 was indexed by the difference in reaction times (RTs) between the predictable (rule-following)
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30 trials and trials in which the stimulus' location changed randomly. Despite observing overall
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32 slower RTs, the authors did not detect a learning deficit associated with ASD. Furthermore, an
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34 assessment of explicit sequence knowledge administered to a subset of the participants failed to
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36 show differences between the group with ASD and the group with TD. However, as absence of
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38 evidence is not evidence of absence, we challenge the notion that individuals with ASD have an
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40 intact functioning of IL because they don't show deficits in some specific tasks.
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50 We propose that the failure to find evidence for an IL deficit in individuals with ASD symptoms
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52 or diagnosis could be explained by the fact that most past studies have employed non-social,
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54 simple stimuli (letter strings, dots etc.). Furthermore, based on empirical findings, we suggest
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56 that when presented with simple/artificial stimuli, participants with ASD might compensate for
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4 deficits in IL tasks by using more effortful, explicit types of learning. Specifically, the same
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6 behavioral outcome can be supported by different neural processes between individuals with TD
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8 and individuals with ASD (generally referred to as compensatory processing; for details, see
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10 Livingston & Happé, 2017). Case in point for IL research, Zwart et al. (2017) asked individuals
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12 with TD and individuals with ASD to perform an IL task with simple surface stimuli (i.e., spatial
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14 locations) while their brain activity was recorded using EEG. From a behavioral standpoint, their
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16 results were similar between the two groups, consistent with the conclusions of Foti et al. (2015).
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18 However, the EEG data revealed distinct patterns of brain activation in the two groups. Namely,
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20 the individuals with TD demonstrated enhanced incidental or unconscious learning, as indicated
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22 by an increase in the N2b component; while the individuals with ASD demonstrated increased
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24 intentional or conscious learning, as indicated by an increase in the P3 component. Thus, the
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26 authors concluded that even though there were no significant behavioral differences between the
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28 groups, individuals with ASD had a greater propensity for using explicit (or intentional) learning
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30 strategies even when IL might have been more appropriate. As the authors put it “*it is very*
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32 *plausible that this intentional learning has adverse effects in more complex social situations, and*
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34 *hence contributes to the social impairments found in ASD*” (Zwart et al., 2017, p. 1). In sum, we
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36 argue that individuals with ASD’s typical behavioral performance in IL tasks that employ simple
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38 surface stimuli is likely sustained by compensatory processing – that would probably stop being
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40 effective in IL tasks with more complex and socially relevant stimuli (we will further elaborate
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42 on this supposition in the paragraph below).
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52 A second important aspect that we wish to emphasize is that most of the research on the IL
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54 deficit in ASD hypothesis has primarily conducted broad assessments. Specifically, when
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56 researchers failed to detect an IL deficit within this population, based on their specific
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4 experimental methods and *particular* (artificial) stimuli, they often concluded that individuals
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6 with ASD do not possess an IL deficit in general. However, it's important to note that even in the
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8 general population, the functioning of IL is influenced by the specific characteristics of the
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10 stimuli upon which it operates (Norman & Price, 2012). For example, in their second
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12 experiment, Eitam et al. (2014) has shown that individuals with TD spontaneously acquire a task
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14 irrelevant artificial grammar instantiated by evolutionarily significant stimuli (i.e., images of
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16 human faces); but, on the contrary, this acquisition does not occur when the task irrelevant
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18 artificial grammar is depicted by less evolutionarily significant stimuli (i.e., images of buildings).
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21 Furthermore, IL operates differently depending on the level of familiarity (Scott & Dienes, 2010)
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23 and perceptual fluency the subjects have with different kinds of stimuli (Perfors & Kidd, 2022).
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25 In this sense, Perfors and Kidd (2022, p.1) found that “... *individual differences [in statistical*
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27 *learning; SL] arise from stimulus-specific variation in perceptual fluency: the ability to rapidly*
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29 *or efficiently code and remember the stimuli that SL occurs over*”. This suggestion becomes even
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31 more relevant to this discussion when we consider that individuals ASD often exhibit atypical
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33 processing of facial cues (e.g., Dawson et al., 2005; Riby et al., 2009; Weigelt et al., 2012). This
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35 implies that they may struggle with extracting visual information from human faces.
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37 Consequently, it stands to reason that any potential deficits in IL within the ASD population
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39 would become particularly evident in tasks involving complex stimuli, where compensatory
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41 processing is more challenging for them. For instance, utilizing emotional facial expressions as
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43 stimuli in such tasks could reveal these deficits more prominently. Preliminary evidence from
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45 studies conducted on subclinical samples suggests that higher levels of autistic traits are indeed
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47 predictive of learning deficits when participants are assessed using socio-emotionally relevant
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49 stimuli. Below we will present some of the more relevant literature on this topic.
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In an extension of Costea (2018) we investigated whether autistic traits in the general population predict deficits in implicitly and explicitly acquiring cognitive structures with socio-emotional components. A total of 282 participants¹ were asked to complete an adapted version of Reber's (01967) artificial grammar learning task. Participants were asked to memorize several strings composed of five different facial emotional expressions. They were unaware these strings followed a grammatical structure. In the test phase, participants classified novel strings depicted by socio-emotional stimuli, identifying which adhered to the same grammar as the original strings. Only half of the novel strings followed the same grammar. We found that a 1-point increase in an autistic traits measure predicted a 0,2-points decrement in the overall classification accuracy and our data were 4 time more likely to support the alternative hypothesis than its null model. Converging evidence was also found by other investigations that used socially relevant visual stimuli (i.e., Hudson et al., 2012; Jellema et al., 2024) or, socially relevant auditory stimuli (i.e., Li et al., 2022). In sum, these research directions seem to challenge the prevailing viewpoint from the literature. Specifically, while IL appears to function normally in clinical samples with ASD when artificial and simple surface stimuli are used, the research above reveals that the use of socio-emotionally relevant surface stimuli, result in learning deficits even at subthreshold levels of autistic traits – this line of evidence constitutes the central pillar of the current investigation.

1.1 The current study

Albeit interesting, the research described above has at least an important limitation in that it only assessed subthreshold autistic traits in the general population, limiting predictions for IL's clinical functioning. Overcoming this limitation requires a novel research design, driven by the

¹ The aggregated data set is publicly available here: <https://osf.io/3ejzk/>

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4 intriguing preliminary results with subclinical participants. This novel research is additionally
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6 motivated by the fact that most previous research has looked at the overall learning effect in
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8 ASD and has overlooked its conscious or unconscious nature. Thus, in this investigation, we will
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10 recruit individuals with a confirmed diagnosis of ASD and individuals with TD and will ask
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12 them to complete our socio-emotional variation of the AGL task to retest the IL deficit in ASD
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14 hypothesis with stimuli that are more relevant for social functioning. By comparing the TD and
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16 the ASD group accuracy, we would be able to assess whether individuals with ASD have an
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18 overall deficit in acquiring artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotionally relevant
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20 information. However, this comparison would not allow us to isolate the potential source of this
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22 difference. Put differently, this overall comparison would be unable to indicate if the potential
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24 deficit is caused by a malfunction in acquiring knowledge implicitly or explicitly. To probe this,
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26 following each classification decision (i.e., distinguishing between grammatical and
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28 ungrammatical strings), we will assess participants' awareness of the acquired knowledge by
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30 prompting them to indicate the subjective basis for their decision. This process will be facilitated
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32 through a modified procedure, first employed by Dienes and Scott (2005). Below we will outline
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34 its theoretical underpinnings.
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43 Given that consciousness stands as one of the most enigmatic phenomena in science (Chalmers,
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45 1995), it is somewhat unsurprising that the methods used to measure it spark intense debates.
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47 Case in point, some advocate for the superiority of objective measures (e.g., the Process
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49 Dissociation Procedure; Destrebecqz & Cleeremans, 2001; Jacoby, 1991). Yet, while these
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51 methods are elegant, research suggests that participants can often pass their criteria for conscious
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53 knowledge even when they cannot articulate what guided their performance (e.g., on intuitive
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55 feelings; Fu et al., 2010, 2018). To this end, Dienes and Scott (2005) developed a methodology
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4 to subjectively evaluate awareness. The authors distinguish two types of knowledge that can be
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6 extracted from IL tasks: structural knowledge and judgement knowledge. Judgment knowledge is
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8 instance specific (e.g., colloquially, “*I know that you are sad*” or, for IL, “*I know that this string*
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10 *is grammatical*”) and develops on top of more general knowledge – structural knowledge (e.g.,
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12 colloquially “*I know the characteristics of sadness*” or, relevant for IL “*I know that this string is*
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14 *grammatical because it follows an ABAB pattern, such as the acquisition ones*”). In their
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16 approach, one must verify the conscious status of both structural and judgement knowledge
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18 because, depending on it a different phenomenology can emerge. First, conscious structural
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20 knowledge only allows for the development of conscious judgement knowledge, leading to
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22 conscious recollections of *rules* or of *memories*. However, second, unconscious structural
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24 knowledge allows for the development of either conscious or unconscious judgement knowledge.
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26 Conscious judgement knowledge developed over unconscious structural knowledge takes the
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28 form of *intuition* or *familiarity* while unconscious structural knowledge developed over
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30 unconscious judgement knowledge feels as *guessing*.
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38 To evaluate awareness of knowledge within our (s-e)AGL task, participants will indicate the
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40 subjective basis of their response after each classification decision. In all trials where awareness
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42 measures will be taken, colloquial but precise definitions of their response options will be
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44 provided. To accommodate the potential challenges faced by individuals with ASD in
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46 differentiating between very similar descriptions of internal mental states, we opt for a simplified
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48 approach to perform the knowledge attributions. Specifically, rather than requiring participants
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50 to discern between fine-tuned categories of guess, intuition, familiarity, rules, or memories, we'll
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52 provide more general response options. To indicate the basis of their previous classification
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54 participants will chose between:
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1. “Random choice – meaning: a pure guess, no reason or feeling guided my answer; I answered as if I were rolling the dice” (this response option reflects unconscious judgment knowledge developed over unconscious structural knowledge).
2. “Feeling – meaning: some overall feeling without being able to say what gave me that feeling” (this response option reflects conscious judgment knowledge developed over unconscious structural knowledge).
3. “Rule or memory – meaning: a reason (rule or memory) that I could tell if I was asked. You can choose rule or memory, even though you are not sure that the information you remember is correct” (this response option reflects conscious judgment knowledge developed over conscious structural knowledge).

Building upon the study overview provided above, we will present the specific objectives and their underlying hypotheses to be examined, as detailed in the subsequent subsection.

1.2 Objectives and Hypotheses

In this paper, we aim to investigate whether individuals with ASD are characterized by abnormalities in both implicit and explicit learning of artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotionally relevant stimuli. Next, we will outline our specific objectives and their corresponding hypotheses:

1.2.1 Primary objectives and hypotheses

1. Overall acquisition: We aim to assess whether ASD is characterized by a global deficit implicitly and explicitly learning cognitive structures depicted by socioemotional components. Thus, we hypothesize that *(H1) participants with ASD will show a smaller test accuracy compared to those with TD.*

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2. Conscious Acquisition: We aim to assess whether ASD is characterized by an advantage in explicit learning. Thus, we hypothesize that *(H2) participants with ASD will show a greater overall explicit learning effect compared to those with TD.*
3. IL Deficit: We aim to explore whether ASD is characterized by a deficit in IL. We predict that *(H3) participants with ASD will demonstrate less accurate unconscious knowledge compared to TD participants.*
4. Compensatory Processing Strategy: We hypothesize that individuals with ASD may employ compensatory processing strategies. Specifically, we predict that *(H4) participants with ASD will attribute more test trials to explicit structural knowledge than TD participants.*

1.2.2 Secondary objectives and hypotheses

5. Symptom Severity as Predictor for Learning: We aim to assess whether the severity of ASD symptoms (measured continuously) predicts explicit learning advantage in learning artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional components. We hypothesize that *(H5) greater levels of ASD symptomatology will positively predict the explicit learning effect.*
6. Symptom Severity as Predictor for explicit learning: Similarly, we aim to determine whether the severity of ASD symptoms predicts the explicit learning of artificial grammars. We expect that *(H6) greater levels of ASD symptomatology will positively predict the explicit learning effect.*
7. Symptom Severity as Predictor for IL: We aim to determine whether the severity of ASD symptoms predicts the IL of artificial grammars. We expect that *(H7) greater levels of ASD symptomatology will negatively predict the IL effect.*
8. Symptom Severity as Predictor for Compensatory Processing: Lastly, we aim to assess whether symptom severity in ASD predicts compensatory processing when learning

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4 artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional stimuli. We hypothesize that (*H8*)
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6 *greater levels of ASD symptomatology will positively predict compensatory processing.*
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10 **2 METHODS**

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12 **2.1 Participants**

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15 This study received the ethical approval of the Ethical Committee of Babeş-Bolyai University
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17 under the reference number 7150/24.05.2024. We will use a between-groups design to compare
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19 performance on the (s-e)AGL task between individuals with ASD and those with TD.
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21 Participants from both groups will be recruited from a pool of pre-screened participants on
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23 Prolific (n.d.), with inclusion criteria including fluency in English, absence of language-related
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25 disorders, and a minimum approval rate of 90% for previously completed tasks on Prolific, with
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27 a completion record of at least three tasks (Peer et al., 2022). Additionally, the ASD group will
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29 consist of individuals who (a) reported a long-term health condition or disability in the form of
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31 ASD, (b) declared that they have received a diagnosis of ASD from a qualified medical
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33 specialist², and (c) score above the 14 points cut-of value on a screening test for autistic
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35 symptoms (i.e., the RAADS-14; Eriksson et al., 2013). The control group will comprise
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37 individuals who (a) reported not having received an ASD diagnosis and (b) score below 14
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39 points on the RAADS-14. We aim to achieve gender balance within our sample by employing a
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41 systematic alternation between male and female participants during data collection. Participants
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43 will be compensated approximately \$10 per hour of participation.
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56 ² The ASD group will consist of individuals that when presented with the question “Have you received a formal
57 clinical diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder, made by a psychiatrist, psychologist, or other qualified medical
58 specialist? This includes Asperger’s syndrome, Autism Disorder, High Functioning Autism or Pervasive
59 Developmental Disorder” have declared: “yes as a child” and “yes, as an adult” however, we will not allow
60 participation to the ones that chose: “I am in the process of receiving a diagnosis”, “No - but I identify as being on
61 the autism spectrum”, “Don't know / rather not say” or “no”.

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Data collection will terminate upon reaching a Bayesian stopping rule for H1-H4. Specifically, this occurs when the Bayes Factor (B) falls below 1/6 or reaches values equal to or greater than 6. To maintain manageable costs associated with this research, we will conclude data collection after obtaining data from a total of 300 participants, with 150 in each group, even if our stopping rule is not satisfied. Initially, we will gather data from 50 participants for each group before conducting analyses. If the stopping rule is not met, we will continue recruiting participants in subsamples of 20 for each group until we either confirm or refute our hypotheses or reach our maximum sample size. Currently, Prolific lists approximately 1200 eligible participants for the ASD group. Given this ceiling value, we have set a realistic recruitment target of approximately 1/8 of the available population for our study. However, this sample size is approximately 10 times larger than most studies investigating this research question. Finally, if we fail to confirm or refute our hypotheses even with a large sample size like this one, it suggests that the relevance of this effect to real-life scenarios, which are often much noisier, is extremely limited and of minimal clinical significance.

2.2 Tasks and materials

Our methodology comprises three distinct tasks. Firstly, we will evaluate participants' comprehension abilities to ensure they have the capacity to understand our instructions. Secondly, we will induce and assess the implicit and explicit acquisition of cognitive structures depicted by socio-emotionally relevant surface stimuli, comparing performance between the ASD and TD conditions. Finally, we will assess participants' ASD symptomatology, anticipating increased levels in the ASD group and decreased levels in the TD group, validating the effectiveness of our sampling strategy. In the following subsections, we will elaborate on each of these tasks. All methodology, instruments, and stimuli for this investigation are openly

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accessible on our Open Materials page (Gorilla Experiment Builder, n.d.) at the following URL:

<https://app.gorilla.sc/openmaterials/805718>.

2.2.1 Comprehension assessment

We integrated an independent Comprehension sample task from the Gorilla Experiment Builder (Anwyl-Irvine et al., 2018) to act as a control mechanism, filtering out participants who may struggle with instruction comprehension, thus decreasing the chances of obtaining false positive differences between our experimental conditions. This task presents text segments followed by comprehension questions. Participants read brief descriptions of historical figures and respond to forced-choice questions demonstrating their understanding. For each figure, participants review key contributions or life events, then select the single appropriate answer probing specific details like inventions, events, or discoveries associated with the figure. The text provided to participants contained all necessary information for accurate responses, requiring no prior semantic knowledge. After completing the comprehension task, participants will receive feedback on the number of correct answers and their accuracy percentage. Those scoring below a predetermined threshold of 75% accuracy will be automatically directed out of the experiment, ensuring exclusion of participants with inadequate comprehension. They will also be prevented from re-enrolling in the experiment. For a sample comprehension item, refer to Table 1 below, and for a complete description of all the comprehension items, see Supplementary Materials. In a feasibility pilot study in which we recruited 5 participants with ASD and run the exact same method as described above, all of them were able to pass our comprehension criteria.

Table 1.

Comprehension items

Archimedes is the best-known mathematician, scientist and inventor from ancient times. He was born on the island of Sicily in 287 BC.

4 He invented the Archimedes Screw which is used to lift water from a lower level to a higher
5 level.
6 It's still used today to lift finely divided solids such as ash, grain, and sand.
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11 Probing questions
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13 Which paragraph introduces his invention?
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15 Which paragraph tells us when he was alive?
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19 **Note.** *The table presents three paragraphs listed on a screen. Participants are asked to read*
20 *them carefully. In another two screens the paragraphs reappear alongside one of the two*
21 *questions. To progress, participants are asked to click on one of the three paragraphs that*
22 *contain the answer to the question that they are asked.*
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25 2.2.2 The socio-emotional artificial grammar learning task

26 This task consists of two phases. Firstly, participants will undergo an acquisition phase, during
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28 which we will expose them to conditions known to activate knowledge acquisition. Secondly, in
29 the test phase, we will assess the conscious and unconscious status of the knowledge that was
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31 acquired during the acquisition phase. Below, we outline the key aspects of both phases (cf.
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33 Jurchis et al. 2023).
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39 2.2.3 The acquisition phase

40 In the acquisition phase, participants will be asked to memorize sequences of emotional facial
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42 expressions of an individual that will be presented on a computer screen. Before starting the task,
43 they will be familiarized with the range of emotional expressions. For a representation, see
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45 Figure 1.
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Figure 1. Depicts the emotional facial expressions of a single individual that will be used to construct the acquisition sequences. facial expressions are extracted from Karolinska Directed Emotional Faces (KDEF; Lundqvist et al., 1998). Access to semantic descriptions of these stimuli are not necessary for obtaining a high task performance as it will not require participants to name any of the presented socio-emotional material.

Unbeknownst to the participants, the sequences of emotional facial expressions will not be composed at random but will follow one of two complex hidden grammars taken from Dienes et al. (1995). For a graphic representation of our implementation, see Figure 2.

Figure 2. Adapted from Dienes et al. (1995), replacing letters with emotional facial expressions: fear for "X", happiness for "R", sadness for "V", a neutral state for "T", and anger for "M". This approach aligns with similar methodologies (e.g., Jurchis et al., 2023).

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6 Both grammars are constructed based on networks featuring an entry point (on the left) and an
7 exit point (on the right). Arrows denote the direction in which each network can be traversed.
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10 When moving between nodes in each network, a string element is generated – for a
11 representation of a grammatical string according to each both grammars, see Figure 3. Strings
12 composed of these elements are grammatical within their respective networks. Conversely,
13 strings not conforming to the rules of a specific grammar are considered non-grammatical (i.e.,
14 strings composed within the network of grammar A are ungrammatical from the perspective of
15 grammar B). Our adaptation did not affect the control properties of Dienes et al. (1995).
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18 Specifically, strings within loops can be eluded completely or may repeat for a maximum of
19 three times (e.g., In the top loop of grammar A, anger can appear between 0 and three
20 consecutive times within a string passing through that node). Both grammars share identical
21 initial bigrams, defined as the sequence of two consecutive string instances, as well as identical
22 exit elements – i.e., in both grammars, all strings begin with an expression of anger. Moreover,
23 the length of the strings can be evenly distributed across grammars, ranging from five to nine
24 possible elements in each one.
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Figure 3. Illustrates two strings conforming to distinct artificial grammars. The string at the top corresponds to the string "VTVTRTTVM" from Grammar A, while the string at the bottom corresponds to the string "VVRMVRMTM" from Grammar B by Dienes et al. (1995).

Participants will view 32 separate sequences, each repeated twice across two blocks, totaling 64 strings. These blocks will be interspersed with 30-second rest breaks. Each string will be displayed on the screen for 12 seconds. We will employ a balanced randomization method to assign participants from both groups to their respective learning grammars. Half of the participants will complete the task using grammar A as their learning grammar, while the remaining half will complete the acquisition phase with grammar B. This strategy ensures that any potential differences that will be observed between the two groups are not caused by internal features of the grammar.

To minimize potential differences between our groups stemming from lack of attention to the task, we will incorporate attention checks throughout the acquisition phase. These checks will occur at randomly determined locations of the task, prompting participants to compare the current sequence of images with a previous one. Participants will have 12 seconds to respond, indicating whether they believe the sequences are identical ('yes' response) or different ('no' response). Within each block, the attention checks will consist of two trials. One trial will present the exact previously displayed sequence, while the other will present a different sequence. Thus,

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out of the four attention checks, two will require a 'yes' response and two will require a 'no' response. This probing will serve as a positive control strategy ensuring active processing of the acquisition material. Participants that will have an accuracy of below 75% at the attention checks will have their data being excluded from the analyses.

2.2.4 The test phase

After the Acquisition phase, participants will be informed about the presence of grammatical rules governing the strings of emotional facial expressions, though the specifics of the underlying grammars will remain undisclosed to them. Participants will then be informed that they will be exposed to a novel set of strings of emotional expressions, some adhering to the same grammar as the previous phase and some of them breaking-it. Regardless of the grammar encountered in the acquisition phase, during the test phase, all participants will receive a randomized sequence of 20 strings conforming to grammar A and 20 strings conforming to grammar B. Thus, test strings adhering to grammar A will be ungrammatical for participants that will complete the acquisition phase with grammar B, and test strings conforming to grammar B will be ungrammatical for participants that will complete the acquisition phase with grammar A. Participants will be tasked with determining whether each string followed the rules of the previous phase. Achieving a performance in the classification task above chance level (i.e., 50%) typically indicates learning. However, to test our hypotheses we will need to determine if responses are performed based on implicitly or explicitly acquired knowledge. Thus, following each response, subjective measures of awareness will be taken. Participants will be asked to complete the stamen: "My last answer was based on a:" by choosing one of the following options: (a) random choice, (b) feeling or, (c) rule or memory. Definitions of these response options will appear every time participants will be asked to indicate the subjective basis of their response, see *Table 2* below.

5 **Table 2.**
 6

Response option	Definition
random choice	a pure guess, no reason or feeling guided my answer; I answered as if I were rolling the dice.
feeling	some overall feeling without being able to say what gave me that feeling.
rules or memory	a reason (rule or memory) I could tell if I was asked. You can choose *rule or memory*, even if you are not sure that the information you remember is correct.

10 Note. Table 2 outlines response options for participants to indicate the subjective basis of their
 11 classification decision during the test phase. Participants will complete the statement "My last
 12 response was based on a..." by selecting from the provided options.
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23 For the analytic purposes of this paper, we will consider that explicit learning will be indexed by
 24 participants' accuracy in the trials where they will indicate that they response was based on
 25 explicit structural knowledge – i.e., "*rules or memory*". Instead, IL will be indexed by
 26 participants accuracy in the trials where they will indicate that their response is based on implicit
 27 structural knowledge – i.e., "*random choice*" and "*feeling*" (for additional information on this
 28 analytic strategy, see e.g., Costea, 2018; Jurchis et al., 2023; Norman & Price, 2012; Scott &
 29 Dienes, 2008).
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46 2.2.5 The self-report screening of ASD symptomatology

47 The Ritvo Autism and Asperger Diagnostic Scale-14 (RAADS-14; Eriksson et al., 2013) is a 14
 48 item self-report measure designed to assess ASD symptomatology in adult populations.
 49 Developed as a shorter alternative to the Ritvo Autism and Asperger Diagnostic Scale-Revised, it
 50 focuses on core ASD symptoms including mentalizing deficits, social anxiety, and sensory
 51 reactivity. Each item is scored on a Likert scale ranging from 0 to 3, with higher scores
 52 indicating greater ASD symptomatology. The questionnaire demonstrates good internal
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4 consistency and test-retest reliability, making it a reliable tool for identifying ASD traits in
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6 clinical and research settings. In the validation study, a cutoff value of 14 points demonstrated a
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8 sensitivity of 97% and a specificity ranging from 46% to 64% (Eriksson et al., 2013). We will
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10 adopt this cutoff score to validate our sampling strategy for the current research. Thus, TD
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12 participants with scores above 14 points on the RAADS will be excluded from data analyses.
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14 Similarly, ASD participants with scores below the 14-point cutoff will also be excluded from
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16 analyses. For the complete list of items comprising this questionnaire, see *Supplementary*
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18 *materials* or the validation study, (Eriksson et al., 2013).
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22 2.3 Procedure

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25 Participants will complete the entire experiment online on their personal computers; smartphone
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27 and tablet completion options will be disabled, to ensure accurate presentation of our stimuli.
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30 Participants who meet the inclusion criteria and do not meet the exclusion criteria will be
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32 directed to the experiment's Gorilla server from the Prolific recruiting platform. Demographic
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34 data will not be reported again, as it will be automatically added from their Prolific profile. Once
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36 on the Gorilla servers, participants will start with a comprehension test. Those who fail to meet a
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38 threshold will be excluded from the experiment. Then, they will be delivered the instructions for
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40 the acquisition phase of the (s-e)AGL task, Attention checks will be implemented during the
41
42 acquisition phase, and participants who fail these checks will have their data removed from the
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44 analyses. Next, participants will complete the test phase instructions, followed by a
45
46 comprehension quiz, and then the test phase of the (s-e)AGL task. Then participants in both
47
48 groups will complete the RAADS-14. Finally, participants will be automatically redirected from
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50 the Gorilla servers to the Prolific platform with a completion token, pending experimenter
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52 approval to receive financial compensation. All participants that will pass the comprehension
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4 task and will reach the end of the task will be compensated in full (i.e., 10 US\$ / hour),
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6 regardless of their performance in the task or in the attention checks. Based on a feasibility pilot
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8 with 5 participants with a reported ASD diagnosis, the entire experiment is anticipated to take
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10 between 35 to 42 minutes.
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12 2.4 The analytical approach 13

14 In this study we hypothesize that individuals with ASD will exhibit differences in overall learning,
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16 explicit learning, IL, and compensatory processing compared to individuals with TD, and that
17
18 these differences will be predicted by the severity of ASD symptoms³. If we will run the
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20 experiment and, after we will conduct the null hypothesis significance testing (NHST), we will get
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22 significant levels greater than .05, we would be unable to interpret these results in the context of
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24 our theory because, as Altman and Bland (1995) put it, absence of evidence is not evidence of
25
26 absence. All we could infer is that we did not find evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This
27
28 limitation arises because NHST procedures do not directly compare the support for the alternative
29
30 hypothesis with that for the null hypothesis (Dienes, 2021b). Some scholars have argued that this
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32 family of tests does not represent a “severe” test of the alternative hypothesis. More specifically,
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34 according to Dienes (2021) a test of the hypothesis is severe if it allows one to collect evidence
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36 against it if the hypothesis is false. We remind that most of the investigations concluded normal
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38 IL functioning in ASD based on lack of evidence for a deficit. Crucially, in the context of our
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40 theoretical argumentation, it would be useful to know if our theory (i.e., hypotheses) are false –
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42 thereby entailing that, as opposed to our suggestion, surface stimuli do not produce IL-related
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54 ³ Specifically, it is hypothesized that individuals with ASD will show: Less overall learning
55 effect compared to TD individuals (H1); More explicit learning (H2); Less accurate unconscious
56 knowledge (H3); Greater reliance on explicit structural knowledge (H4); Greater severity of
57 ASD symptoms will negatively predict learning effects (H5), explicit learning effects (H6),
58 implicit learning effects (H7), and finally, greater use of explicit learning strategies (H8).
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4 deficits in ASD. To this end, Bayesian analyses gained traction in the more recent psychological
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6 literature (for a review, see Heck et al., 2022). This approach offers a continuous measure of
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8 confidence in the alternative hypothesis relative to the null hypothesis. More important for our
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10 discussion above, Bayesian analyses allow for confirmation of the null hypothesis. For all
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12 hypotheses that will be tested, in line with common practice, we'll interpret Bayes factors ("B") as
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14 follows: values between 3 and 10 suggest moderate evidence in support of the alternative
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16 hypothesis, while B values of 10 or greater indicate strong evidence. For B values between 0.10
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18 and 0.33, indicate moderate evidence favoring the null hypothesis, and B values less than or equal
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20 to 0,10 provide strong evidence for the null. Values between 0.33 and 3 are considered insensitive
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22 in their interpretation (for further details, see Lee & Wagenmakers, 2014). Instead of using default
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24 values for Bayesian testing, we will construct distributions of priors informed by our past research
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26 with accessible data or the most relevant theoretical findings from the literature. For simplicity,
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28 related hypotheses will share the same prior distribution. In the subsection below, we will either
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30 detail the rationale for our prior distribution or explicitly reference the prior used for each specific
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32 hypothesis. To assess the robustness of each B , we will report Robustness Regions (RR), showing
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34 the range of H1 model means that yield the same conclusions as the reported B (support for H1,
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36 H0, or insensitive data; e.g., Dienes, 2021). All NHST will be computed with $\alpha=.05$. When
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38 interpreting our findings we will always draw conclusions based on the Bayesian analyses. All,
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40 analyses will be conducted in JASP, using the General Bayesian Test module for Bayesian
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42 analyses (JASP Team, 2024). For an overview of our hypotheses, analytic decisions and derived
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44 interpretations depending on different outcomes, consult *Table 3*.
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4 2.5 Planned comparisons

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6 2.5.1 Primary comparisons

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8 2.5.1.1 Overall acquisition

9 *H1* states that *participants with ASD will show lower overall test accuracy compared to those*
10 *with TD*. To verify-it we will use an independent sample *t-test* to compare the accuracy between
11
12 the two groups. For the Bayesian analysis, we estimate the distribution of priors based on the
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14 extension of Costea (2018a)⁴, where 282 participants completed an AGL task with socio-
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16 emotional stimuli and had their autistic traits measured using the Subthreshold Autistic Traits
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18 Questionnaire (SATQ; Kanne et al., 2012). In this sample, the mean SATQ score was 23.86 (SD
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20 = 8.26) with a median of 23. To model our priors, we performed a median split on this dataset
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22 and conducted an independent sample *t-test* comparing the overall accuracy of participants with
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24 low autistic traits (below the median) and high autistic traits (above the median), excluding those
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26 who scored exactly at the median. Results indicated that the low autistic traits group had
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28 significantly better accuracy than the high autistic traits group, $t(266) = 2.48$, $M_{difference} = 3.64$
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30 [95% CI = 0.75 – 6.54], $d = 0.3$, $p = .007$. Considering that in our sample there were only
31
32 participants from the general population, without any diagnosis of ASD, we expect to observe a
33
34 greater difference in accuracy between the TD and ASD groups than we observed between the
35
36 low and high autistic traits groups. To reflect this expectation, we will compute a Bayesian
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38 independent sample *t-test* with priors modeled as a normal distribution with a mean equal to the
39
40 upper bound of the 95%CI difference that we observed in the general population (i.e., 6.5%) and
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42 a standard deviation of half the mean value (i.e., 3.25%).
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53 2.5.1.2 Conscious Acquisition

54 *H2* states that *participants with ASD will show a greater explicit learning effect compared to*
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56 *those with TD*. To test this hypothesis, an independent samples *t-test* will compare the accuracies
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60 ⁴ The aggregated data set is available here: <https://osf.io/3ejzk/>

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of the test trials in which participants reported relying on rules or memory between the two groups. H2 will use the same prior distribution as H1.

2.5.1.3 *IL Deficit*

H3 predicts that participants *with ASD will demonstrate less accurate unconscious knowledge compared to TD participants*. This will be assessed by an independent samples *t-test* comparing the accuracies of test trials based on unconscious structural knowledge between the two groups. H3 will use the same prior distribution as H1.

2.5.1.4 *Compensatory Processing Strategy*

H4 predicts that *participants with ASD will attribute more test trials to explicit structural knowledge than TD participants*. This will be examined by an independent samples *t-test* that will compare the proportion of trials attributed to explicit structural knowledge between the two groups, regardless of their accuracy. The independent sample Bayesian *t-test* will be conducted using a normal prior distribution with a mean representing an expected effect of 10% and a standard deviation of $m/2$ ($B_{N[10\%; 5\%]}$). This anticipated 10% difference between the two groups is based on findings by Dienes and Scott (2005). In their second experiment, participants were instructed to complete a standard AGL task. Results indicated that those who were instructed to intentionally look for rules exhibited a 10% higher proportion of explicit attributions compared to the control group, who completed the AGL task under standard instructions. This estimate assumes that individuals with ASD engaging in compensatory processing will demonstrate similar behavior with individuals with TD that are actively attempting to decipher the underlying rules of the AGL task.

2.5.2 Secondary comparisons

2.5.2.1 *Symptom Severity as Predictor for Learning*

H5 states that *greater levels of ASD symptomatology will negatively predict the overall learning effect*. This will be tested through a regression analysis using participants' RAADS-14 scores as

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the IV and their test accuracy as the DV. To model our priors for H5 we will employ a similar solution to the ratio of scales heuristic proposed by Dienes (2019) for computing Bayes factors on regression coefficients. Here we assume that, on average, participants in the ASD group will demonstrate a test phase accuracy lower with 6.5% than participants in the TD group (see H1).

Then, we note that RAADS-14 is an instrument that allows scores from 0 to 42 points. Thus, in a liberal estimate, each 1-point increase in the RAADS-14 should predict a 0.15% decrease in test phase accuracy. However, the validation study of the RAADS-14 (Eriksson et al., 2013) found that the average score in their TD sample was 3.9 and in their ASD sample was 27.9 points.

Thus, in a more conservative estimate, a difference in 24 points between the two samples would predict a 6.5% decrement in test phase accuracy. In this scenario, each point on the RADS-14 should account for a 0.27% decrease in test performance. To account for both the liberal and the conservative scenarios, we will model our distribution of priors as a uniform distribution between 0.15% and 0.27% ($B_{U[0.15-0.27]}$).

2.5.2.2 Symptom Severity as Predictor for explicit learning

H6 states that greater levels of ASD symptomatology will predict the explicit learning effect.

This will be examined using a regression analysis with participants' RAADS-14 scores as the IV and their accuracy for the test trials attributed to explicit structural knowledge as the DV. H6 will use the same prior distribution as H5.

2.5.2.3 Symptom Severity as Predictor for IL

H7 states that *greater levels of ASD symptomatology will negatively predict the IL effect*. This

will be examined using a regression analysis with participants' RAADS-14 scores as the IV and their accuracy for the test trials attributed to implicit structural knowledge as the DV. H7 will use the same prior distribution as H5.

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2.5.2.4 *Symptom Severity as Predictor for Compensatory Processing*

H8 states that *greater levels of ASD symptomatology will positively predict compensatory processing*. This will be evaluated through a regression analysis with participants' RAADS-14 scores as the IV and the proportion of test trials attributed to conscious structural knowledge irrespective of their accuracy as the DV. To model our distribution of priors for H7 we will proceed similarly to H5 but use the expected difference of H4 instead of H1. Thus, given that we expect a 10% difference between the ASD and the TD group (based on Dienes & Scott, 2005), in a liberal estimate, each additional RAADS-14 point should account for 0.24% more explicit attributions. However, given the 24 points difference in the RAADS-14 validation study between individuals with TD and with ASD (Eriksson et al., 2013), in a conservative estimate, each point should account for 0.42% increase in explicit attributions. Thus, we will model our distribution of priors as a uniform with values between 0.24% and 0.42% ($B_{U[0.24-0.42]}$).

2.6 Data exclusions and positive controls

To ensure high-quality data, we will implement several exclusion criteria. First, participants from both groups who score below 75% accuracy on comprehension task will be excluded. Second, participants who report a formal diagnosis of ASD but score less than 14 on the RAADS-14 will also be excluded. Third, participants from the TD group that score above 14 points on the RAADS-14 will also be dropped from the analyses. Fifth, participants responding incorrectly to more than one of the four attention checks that will be implemented within the acquisition task will be dropped from the analyses. Sixth, participants with a mean reaction time during the grammatical decision task in the testing phase that is more than 3 standard deviations above their sample's mean will be excluded.

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Table 3. Study design template

Question	Hypothesis	Sampling Plan	Analysis Plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes	Theory that could be shown wrong by the outcomes
<p>Are ASDs characterized by a global deficit to implicitly and explicitly learn cognitive structures depicted by socioemotional components?</p>	<p>H1) Participants with ASD will show lower overall test accuracy compared to participants with TD.</p>	<p>We aim to collect data until we reach a base factor for (i.e., $B \geq 6$) or against (i.e., $B \leq 1/6$) the hypothesis, within the limit of 150 valid data sets / group.</p>	<p>An independent sample t-test will compare the accuracy between the two groups. For the priors we will use a normal distribution with $m = 6.5\%$ and $SD = 3.25\%$.</p>	<p>As per the Cortex journal commitment to the PCI-RR initiative, a value of $B > 6$ will be considered strong evidence and as otherwise commonly practiced, $B > 3$ will be regarded as moderate evidence for H1. Values between 0.33 and 3 will be considered insensitive and values of $B < 0.33$ will be considered evidence for H0.</p>	<p>H1 confirmed: interpreted as proof that individuals with ASD are characterized by an impairment to learn artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional stimuli. H1 rejected: interpreted as proof that individuals with ASD are not characterized by impairments in learning artificial grammars depicted by</p>	<p>Would test the theory/idea that individuals with ASD are characterized by impaired learning from facial expressions.</p>

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					socioo-emotional stimuli.	
<p>23 Are ASDs characterized by an advantage in explicit learning?</p>	<p>24 H2) Participants with ASD will show a greater explicit learning effect compared to participants with TD.</p>	<p>25 Same as for H1.</p>	<p>26 An independent sample t-test will compare the accuracies of the test trials in which participants reported relying on rules or memory between the two groups. H2 will use the same priors as H1.</p>	<p>27 Same as above.</p>	<p>28 H2 confirmed: interpreted as proof that individuals with ASD have a superior ability to explicitly learn artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional stimuli. 29 H2 rejected: interpreted as proof that individuals with ASD do not have a superior ability to explicitly learn artificial grammars depicted by socioo-emotional stimuli.</p>	<p>30 Would test the compensatory processing framework, shedding light on the effectiveness in using atypical cognitive processing that sustains seemingly normal behavioral functioning.</p>
<p>31 Are participants with an ASD characterized by an IL deficit?</p>	<p>32 H3) Participants with ASD will demonstrate less accurate unconscious knowledge</p>	<p>33 Same as for H1.</p>	<p>34 An independent sample t-test will compare test trial accuracies between the two groups for trials</p>	<p>35 Same as above.</p>	<p>36 H3 confirmed: interpreted as proof that individuals with ASD have a deficit in the implicit learning</p>	<p>37 Would test the theory of an implicit learning deficit in ASD.</p>

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	<p>20 compared to TD 21 participants. 22 23 24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40</p>		<p>where participants relied on unconscious structural knowledge.H3 will use the same priors as H1.</p>		<p>of artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional stimuli. H3 rejected: interpreted as proof that individuals with ASD do not have a deficit in the implicit learning of artificial grammars depicted by socioo-emotional stimuli.</p>	
<p>41 42 Are individuals 43 with an ASD 44 employing 45 compensatory 46 processing 47 strategies in the 48 socio-emotional 49 version of the 50 AGL task? 51 52 53 54 55 56 57 58 59 60 61</p>	<p>H4) Participants with ASD will attribute more test trials to explicit structural knowledge than TD participants.</p>	<p>Same as for H1.</p>	<p>An independent samples t-test will compare the proportion of trials attributed to explicit structural knowledge between groups, regardless of accuracy. We will use a normal prior distribution with $m = 10\%$ and $SD = 5\%$.</p>	<p>Same as above.</p>	<p>H4 confirmed: interpreted as proof that individuals with ASD engage in compensatory processing while learning artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional stimuli. H4 rejected: interpreted as proof that individuals with</p>	<p>Would test the compensatory processing framework, highlighting the quantity of compensatory processing in ASD, regardless of its effectiveness.</p>

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					ASD do not engage in compensatory processing while learning artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional stimuli.	
Is the severity of ASD symptoms (measured continuously) a predictor of the effect of learning artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional components?	H5) The level of ASD symptomatology will negatively predict the overall learning effect.	The sample size for the entire study will be set to achieve sensitive evidence (B of 6 or 1/6) for or against hypotheses H1–H4, with a maximum of 150 valid datasets per group. The sample size is not specifically tailored to the current hypothesis. Nonetheless, a B of 6 will be considered strong evidence, while a B of 3	H5 will be tested through a regression analysis using participants’ RAADS-14 scores as the IV and their test accuracy as the DV. We will model our priors as a uniform distribution between 0.15% and 0.27%.	Same as above.	<p>If H1 & H5 confirmed: Interpreted as proof that more severe ASD symptomatology predicts greater overall learning deficits.</p> <p>If H1 confirmed & H5 rejected: interpreted as proof that learning deficits are not gradual but appear in an all-or-nothing manner.</p> <p>If H1 rejected and H5 confirmed: Unlikely with our sampling plan. However,</p>	Similar as for H1.

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		<p>20 21 will be 22 interpreted as 23 moderate 24 evidence. 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 55 56 57 58 59 60</p>			<p>61 if these 62 differences will 63 emerge, they will 64 be interpreted as 65 tentative evidence suggesting that the severity of ASD symptomatology, rather than simple group classification, is a more accurate predictor of the learning effect in the (s-e)AGL task, emphasizing the importance of considering autism as a spectrum extending beyond categorical classification. If H1 & H5 rejected: Interpreted as evidence that ASD symptomatology</p>	
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					does not predict learning outcomes in the (s-e)AGL task.	
Is the severity of ASD symptoms a predictor for the explicit learning of artificial grammars?	H6) The level of ASD symptomatology will predict the explicit learning effect.	Same as for H5.	H6 will be tested by a regression analysis with participants' RAADS-14 scores as the IV and their accuracy for the test trials attributed to explicit structural knowledge as the DV. H6 will use the same prior distribution as H5.	Same as above.	Similar patterns of interpretation as for H5 but with specific focus on the explicit learning effect (i.e., coupled with H2 instead of H1).	Similar as for H2.
Is the severity of ASD symptoms a predictor for the IL of artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional stimuli?	H7) Greater levels of ASD symptomatology will negatively predict the IL effect.	Same as for H5.	H7 will be tested by a regression analysis with participants' RAADS-14 scores as the IV and their accuracy for the test trials	Same as above.	Similar patterns of interpretation as for H5 but with specific focus on the implicit learning effect (i.e., coupled with H3 instead of H1).	Similar as for H3.

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			attributed to implicit structural knowledge as the DV. H7 will use the same prior distribution as H5.			
Does the severity of ASD symptoms predict compensatory processing when learning artificial grammars depicted by socio-emotional stimuli?	H8) The level of ASD symptomatology will positively predict compensatory processing.	Same as for H5.	H8 will be evaluated through a regression analysis with participants' RAADS-14 scores as the IV and the proportion of test trials attributed to conscious structural knowledge irrespective of their accuracy as the DV. We will model our priors as a uniform distribution with values between	Same as above.	Similar patterns of interpretation as for H5 but with specific focus on the compensatory processing effect (i.e., coupled with H4 instead of H1).	Similar as for H4.

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			0.24% and 0.42%.			
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7 **3 DECLARATIONS**

8 **3.1 CRediT Author statement**

9 AC.: Conceptualization, Design, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data collection, Resources,
10 Writing - Original Draft, Funding acquisition, Supervision. RJ. : Conceptualization, Design,
11 Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing - Original Draft. AP.: Methodology, Data Curation,
12 Writing - Original Draft. AO.: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft.
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20 **3.2 Funding statement**

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36

37 **3.4 Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process**

38 During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT to increase the fluency of the
39 text. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and
40 take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.
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4 5 SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

5
6
7 5.1 Study information sheet and consent instructions that will appear on Prolific

8 This single-session study investigates the memory for facial expressions in participants with and
9 without an autism diagnosis. The duration of this study is estimated at 35 minutes. Next, we
10 present a brief description of the procedure. We are going to kindly ask you to complete the
11 following four tasks:
12
13
14
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16

17
18
19 1. A comprehension task. This will last about 2/3 minutes. The performance will not rely on
20 previously learned knowledge. Instead, we give this test because, to ensure data validity, we
21 must be sure that you can understand our instructions. You will be asked 6 questions. If you will
22 answer incorrectly more than twice, we will direct you to the end of the experiment and your
23 application will be rejected. Partial payment for your time will still apply (around £0.38).
24
25
26
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29

30
31 2. The memory task. This task will last about 12/13 minutes. You will be presented with a
32 set of strings that will be made up of different facial expressions. Here, you will be asked to
33 memorize the order of the faces to the best of your ability.
34
35
36
37

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39 3. A decision task. Depending on how fast you will respond, this task will last about 13/14
40 minutes. Here you will be asked to make several decisions and answer one or two self-report
41 questions for each decision.
42
43
44

45
46 4. Complete a 14-item questionnaire. This task will last about 3/5 minutes.

47
48
49 Attention checks will be inserted through the task; however, your application will most likely not
50 be rejected if you will pass the comprehension task. We estimate that you will receive the reward
51 within 7 days after you will complete your submission. Only desktop devices are allowed. Our
52 study does not require audio, camera, microphone, or software downloads. Demographic
53 information and the self-report answers to the fourth task will only be used to describe our
54
55
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samples in the publication that will result from this study. The raw data set will be made publicly available. We will not collect identifying information. This study respects the ethical requirements of Babes-Bolyai University.

If you wish to opt-out of the study, you can do this by simply closing the browser window. Your data will not be archived and your application will be rejected. No reward will be given for voluntary early withdrawals.

5.2 The consent form that will appear after eligible participants will be redirected from Prolific to Gorilla *Consent*

This experiment respects the ethics requirements of the REDACTED University and is being used to explicitly gather data under the form of response choices and demographic information (i.e., age and gender). Identifying information will not be gathered. The anonymized participant-level data set will be made publicly available. You have the right to withdraw at any time - simply close the browser containing this experiment. If you leave the experiment before the end, this will be taken as 'withdrawal' and your data will be deleted.

*By pressing the “**I consent**” button below, you declare that you have read and understood the above and hereby give your consent to take part in this experiment.*

Once they pressed the “I consent” button, they will be directed to the following phases of the experiment.

5.3 The instructions and materials of the comprehension task

5.3.1.1 Instructions

Next, you will complete the comprehension test. It will be based on several historic figures!

Read the text on each screen. When you have finished reading, click Continue. In the next

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4 screen, you will see the same text but you will be asked some questions. Click the paragraph
5
6
7 (line of text) that contains the answer to each question. Press Start when you are ready!
8

9
10 5.3.2 Archimedes

11 Archimedes is the best known mathematician, scientist and inventor from ancient times. He was
12
13 born on the island of Sicily in 287 BC.

14
15
16 He invented the Archimedes Screw which is used to lift water from a lower level to a higher
17
18 level.

19
20
21 It's still used today to lift finely divided solids such as ash, grain, and sand.

22
23
24 Which paragraph introduces his invention?

25
26
27 Which paragraph tells us when he was alive?

28
29 5.3.3 Benjamin Franklin

30 Discovered the Law of Conservation of Electric Charge and proved that lightning is electricity.
31

32
33 He discovered that lightning is electricity by flying a kite in a thunder storm.

34
35
36 He is also one of the Founding Fathers of the United States.

37
38
39 Which paragraph tells us what he discovered?

40
41
42 Which paragraph tells us how he discovered it?

43
44 5.3.4 Louis Pasteur

45 Pasteur invented the process of pasteurization and patented it in 1862.
46

47
48 Pasteurisation kills the microorganisms that can cause food to go bad and so is valuable for
49
50 making food last longer.

51
52
53 During pasteurization, farm and brewery products such as milk, wine and beer are heated briefly
54
55 to a temperature between 60 and 100 degrees centigrade.

56
57
58 Which paragraph tells us what he invented?
59
60
61

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Which paragraph tells us how this is done?

You gave [X number of] incorrect answers, and were Y percent correct!

Message for Low Comprehension and Exclusion from the Experiment:

Our research requires a very good ability to understand written language. Unfortunately, you scored below the threshold in our comprehension test. Therefore, we cannot accept you in this research at this time. And they will be directed to the end of the experiment. However, if they will pass our comprehension inclusion criteria, they will proceed with the task, as will further be presented below.

5.3.5 Demographic Information

Congratulations, you passed our comprehension test. Now, before we continue with the experiment, we ask you to give us some information about you.

What is your age, in years?

Please indicate your gender.

5.4 AGL Acquisition Instructions

Next, several strings of images will appear on your display. Each image will depict an emotional facial expression of an individual. To see an example, click the button below.

[example string 1]

Each of these facial expressions represents a distinct emotion. For now, try to familiarize yourself with them.

During this part of the study, several strings composed of these faces will appear on the screen, but in different combinations; for example:

1. the order of these faces may differ from string to string
2. in some strings, some expressions may appear while some may not

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2
3
4 3. some expressions may appear more than once in a single string

5
6
7 Your task is to watch and try to memorize all the strings. Each one will stay on the screen for 12
8
9 seconds and will appear several times, so it's not a problem if you feel like you can't remember
10
11 them from the beginning. Just try to remember them as best you can, because you will have to do
12
13 a task based on these strings on the next part of the study.
14

15
16
17 Also, at random intervals during this task, you will be asked if the string you are currently seeing
18
19 is identical to the previous string.
20

21
22 1. If you will think that the string you see at that moment is the same as the string that
23
24 appeared before it, you will press the 'yes' button.
25

26
27 2. If you will think that the string you see at that moment is not the same as the string that
28
29 appeared before it, you will press the 'no' button.
30

31
32 You will have 12 seconds to answer. To do a training exercise, press the button below.

33
34
35 [example string 2]

36
37
38 In the task, you will see strings similar to the one above. Remember, your most important task is
39
40 to try to memorize them!

41
42
43 Is this string identical to the previously displayed one?

44
45 [response]: YES/NO

46
47
48 Take a look at the strings below. The top string appeared first and was followed by the bottom
49
50 string.
51

52
53 [example string 3]

54
55 [example string 4]

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Even though the two strings are of equal length and are made up using the same faces, they are different because the order of the faces differs between them. Click the button below to continue, Remember, your most important task is to try to memorize all the strings as best as you can because you will have to do a task later on in the experiment. You start the experiment by pressing the button below

5.5 AGL Test Instructions

The previous strings were not random. The order of the faces in the strings was determined by a set of complex rules. Next, you will see new strings of emotional faces. Some will follow the same rules (these will be called Grammatical strings), and others will not follow them (these will be called Ungrammatical strings). Your task will be to answer two questions for each of the 40 novel strings that you will see.

First

You will have to indicate if the new string is grammatical or not. You will click on the “yes” button if you think that the string is Grammatical or, on the “no” button if you think that the string is Ungrammatical. Keep in mind, the rules are complex and it is possible that you realized them only partially or not at all; it's okay, try to respond the best you can. To continue the instructions, answer this: Let’s say that you think that a new string does not respect the previous rules; then, would you say that this string is grammatical?

[response:] YES/NO

Second

You will have to indicate what your previous response was based on. We explain what “based on” means. Sometimes, participants have a relatively clear idea of what the correct answer would be, based on a rule or memory that they learned and can remember. Often, though, participants

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2
3
4 have only a feeling, an impression that a certain answer is the right one, but they do not know
5
6 exactly what this feeling is based on. Finally, participants might have no idea of what is the
7
8 correct answer and simply try to guess it by choosing at random. You will have to complete the
9
10 statement: “My last answer was based on a:” by choosing one of the following:

- 11
12
13
14 1. random choice – meaning: a pure guess, no reason or feeling guided my answer; I
15
16 answered as if I were rolling the dice.
17
18
19 2. feeling – meaning: some overall feeling without being able to say what gave me that
20
21 feeling.
22
23
24 3. 1. rule or memory – meaning: a reason (rule or memory) that I could tell if I was asked.
25
26 You can choose rule or memory, even though you are not sure that the information you
27
28 remember is correct.
29
30

31
32 These definitions will appear every time you’ll have to use them. There is no right or wrong
33
34 answer – it is extremely important that you chose the option which best describes what you relied
35
36 on.
37

38
39 To continue the instructions, answer this: if you cannot tell exactly why you feel that a string is
40
41 grammatical, you would choose a:
42

- 43
44
45 a. random choice
46
47
48 b. feeling
49
50
51 c. rule or memory
52

53 To sum up, for each string that will be presented, you will be asked to indicate:

- 54
55
56 1. If the new string is grammatical or not (yes /no)
57
58 2. What is the basis of your response (random choice / feeling / rule or memory).
59
60
61

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Depending on how fast you answer, this task should take around 15 minutes. The instructions are over. Click the button below to start.

5.6 Items of the Ritvo Autism and Asperger Diagnostic Scale-14 (RAADS-14; Eriksson et al., 2013)

Please respond with the answer that most accurately describes how each of the statements below applies to you. For the purposes of this test, “When I was Young” refers to the age of 17 or younger. Scroll down this page to see all questions.

5.6.1 Response options

- True Now & When Young
- True Only Now
- True When I Was Young
- Never True

5.6.2 Statemens

1. It is difficult for me to understand how other people are feeling when we are talking.
2. Some ordinary textures that do not bother others feel very offensive when they touch my skin.
3. It is very difficult for me to work and function in groups.
4. It is difficult to figure out what other people expect of me.
5. I often don't know how to act in social situations.
6. I can chat and make small talk with people.
7. When I feel overwhelmed by my senses, I have to isolate myself to shut them down
8. How to make friends and socialize is a mystery to me
9. When talking to someone, I have a hard time telling when it is my turn to talk or to listen
10. Sometimes I have to cover my ears to block out painful noises (like vacuum cleaners or people talking too much or too loudly)

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2
3
4 11. It can be very hard to read someone's face, hand, and body movements when we are
5
6 talking
7

8
9 12. I focus on details rather than the overall idea

10
11 13. I take things too literally, so I often miss what people are trying to say
12

13
14 14. I get extremely upset when the way I like to do things is suddenly changed
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